

Blended Learning in a Language Classroom: Implication for Pedagogy

Abraham Femi Akintunde

Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Fatima Seifeldeen Abdallah ✉

Department of Arts Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examined Blended Learning (BL) and its implication to Language learning. It reviews relevant literature over the last two decades on blended learning generally, and language instruction using blended learning techniques in particular. It discusses the concept of blended learning and its features. The paper further explores the discussion of the positive benefits from applying blended learning in language instruction. The paper also highlights some disadvantages of blended learning course for proper understanding and the practice and implementation of this method. An important part of this paper also explores the implications for pedagogy. The major conclusions of the study are that blending learning enhances the learner's experience of a new language, and offers greater efficiency in the communication and practice of a particular language. Efficient and user-friendly technology, with direction instruction and practice in a face-to-face setting are seen as the key to successful blended learning language instruction. The paper then recommends that teachers should be adequately trained in the art of BL because they are still greatly needed by students for their timely and adequate guidance, direction, feedback and comments while students are learning in blended learning environment.

Keywords: *Blended teaching, blended learning, language instruction, language learning and Information and Communications Technology.*

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Introduction

Blended Learning (BL) is progressively becoming a prospect for higher education student. It permits for the improvement of interface between teachers and learners, using internet or computer based techniques (Djiwandono, 2013). Blended learning courses have become very popular nowadays in every sphere of academics. They are related to those courses in which a substantial amount of seat time, that is, time spent in the classroom, is replaced with online activities that include learners in meeting course objectives (Bock, Modabber, Kniha, Lemos, Rafai, & Holzle, 2018). According

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to Poon (2013) BL courses have been classified between 30% and 79% of the learning materials for online activities and 29% are face-to-face course. Rendering to Garrison and Vaughan (2017), blended learning is the thoughtful fusion of face-to-face and online learning experiences . . . such that the strengths of each are blended into a unique learning experience. It is a fundamental redesign that transforms the structure of, and approach to, teaching and learning". It is a fundamental redesign that transformers the structure of, and approach to, teaching and learning". Blended learning is considered as a significant part of the activities that take place over two different areas: in person and online. Several other pedagogies such as lecture, problem based learning, Just in Time Teaching, cooperative learning, and others can then be covered within the blended framework (Garrison & Vaughan, 2017).

The difficulty that shapes blended learning is to connect, or blend what occurs in each medium so that face-to-face and online activities can strengthen each other to produce a single and unified course. Blended learning courses use effective learning strategies through the implementation of different pedagogical approaches. The asynchronous nature of the blended module of the courses possesses constructive impact of increasing the time learners spend on course material (Poon, 2013). Thoughts showed online inspire reflection and usually reach 100% participation. As a result, the face-to-face time can be used more effectively with learners extending the material beyond what might be achieved in a conventional face -to-face course. The learners in a blended course create more and comfortable networks between what they are learning and what they already know, generating a robust scaffold to establish evidence (Zhao, 2013).

Concept of Blended Learning

BL is not new, contrary to what some may think it has been in use for more than 20 years. It was first used in the corporate world as a strategy to allow employees to continue in the workplace and study at the same time (Sharma, 2011). It also emerged in the educational context as a result of:

- a) the accessibility of computer technology in and outside the classroom;
- b) the expansion of the pedagogical potential of Information, Communications and Technology (ICT) for teaching and learning (Zhao, 2013; and
- c) the disillusionment generated in online learning with the stand-alone adoption of online media (Poon, 2013).

Owing to the problems faced with fully virtual environments (for example, sense of isolation and low motivation), many people started to reject the "either or view of learning online versus face- to-face" (Poon, 2013, p.3) Instead, people resorted to the creation of blended spaces so as to generate more satisfactory outcomes. As Garrison and Vaughan (2017) point out, a balance of media is fundamental to make learning and teaching effective, as "the ICT element is unlikely to contribute to more than 50 per cent of the total strategy" (p.3).

The concept of BL has been addressed by many authors and it has a varied range of meanings. Tayebinik and Puteh (2012) make a comprehensive review of some of the definitions attached to BL. They present those definitions that are more general and conservative as well as those that are more specific and technology-related. Tayebinik and Puteh (2012) provide the broadest definition of all authors since blended learning

is considered as a combination of instructional methods or pedagogical approaches. Authors like Zhao (2013), Poon (2013), and Sharma (2011), however, define blended learning as a mixture of online learning, or web-based training with face-to-face communication and more of traditional methods of learning and teaching. Neumeier (2015) defines BL as a combination of face-to-face (FF) and Computer Assisted Learning (CAL) in a single teaching and learning environment. Sharma (2011) generalizes their understanding of BL as a course which combines face-to-face classroom component with an appropriate use of technology:

...the term technology covers a wide range of recent technologies, such as the Internet, CD-ROMs and interactive white boards. It also includes the use of computers as a means of communication, with applications such as chat and e-mail, and a number of environments which enable teachers to enrich their courses, such as VLEs (Virtual Learning Environments), blogs and wikis (p. 7).

For Sharma (2011), the term blended learning is applicable to a variety of teaching and learning situations and it implies a broad range of combinations with regard to face-to-face and computer-mediated teaching and learning. According to Sharma (2011), BL has attracted different definitions and stances. The term *'blend'* has been used to refer to the mix of teaching modes (CAL and F2F), and also to the combination of technologies (email, phone, web, etc.) methodologies (presentation-practice-production, TBLT, etc.), and probably in the future, real and virtual worlds (e.g. *Second Life*).

Similarly, Djiwandono (2013) state that among the many definitions available, three representative definitions include:

- (a) a learning method with more than one delivery mode being used to optimize learning outcomes and to reduce cost associated with program delivery;
- (b) any mix of instructor-led training methods with technology-based learning; and
- (c) the mix of traditional and interactive- rich forms of classroom training with any of the innovative technologies (p. 28). Djiwandono (2013) proposes six combinations of blended instruction as follows:

- (a) offline and online learning;
- (b) self-paced, live, and collaborative learning;
- (c) structured and unstructured learning;
- (d) custom content with off-the-shelf content;
- (e) work and learning; and
- (f) blending synchronous physical formats, synchronous online formats, and self-paced, asynchronous formats (p. 28).

Nonetheless, Neumeier (2015) notes that despite BL being defined as the mix of CAL and F2F teaching, the distinction between these two models is no longer clear, as classrooms are now equipped with advanced mobile technology. In other words, that is, to talk about face-to-face instruction does not necessarily imply an absence of the use of technology. As Neumeier (2015) states: "It becomes obvious that this distinction becomes increasingly blurred as we interact with, around, at, in relation to and through computers" (p.165). Authors like Sharma (2011) argues that there is nothing new about

BL and that it is named as a response to the logical development of prior pedagogical tendencies involving the mixing of methods of teaching. Yet, some authors contend that there might be nothing new about BL. Institutions that use blended approaches, as Neumeier (2015) observes, base their practices on the idea that both face-to-face interaction and online methods have inherent advantages, and therefore are beneficial for teachers and learners. According to Tayebinik and Puteh (2012) in agreement with Sharma (2011) and Poon (2013) blended instruction offers teachers the possibility to spend more time with learners in both small groups and individually, and can create a flexible and active learning environment that has the potential to change students' experiences and outcomes. Their cited reasons for using blended instruction to include: "improved pedagogy, easy access to knowledge, more interaction among learners, personal presence, cost effectiveness, and ease of revision of learning content" (Tayebinik & Puteh, 2012, p. 28).

The most important aim of a BL design is thus to create a learning environment that combines the best of both models and that which works as a whole and to find "the most effective and efficient combination of the two modes of learning for the individual learning subjects, contexts and objectives" (Neumeier, 2015, p. 165). BL seeks to generate a coherent and harmonious balance between online access to knowledge and face-to-face human interaction by taking into account learners' and teachers' aptitudes and attitudes. BL therefore remains an important concept in language teaching as "its overall focus is concerned with the attempt to identify the optimum mix of course delivery in order to provide the most effective language learning experience" (Sharma, 2011, p. 457). In this task of creating a balanced blended learning environment, it is crucial to consider the various uses of online media so as to be able to distinguish BL from the ICT use that commonly takes place in the classroom. According to Poon (2013), online media can be used in *'adjunct'* or in *'mixed'* modes. In the former, technology is used to enhance traditional face-to-face instruction, while in the latter; a significant portion of the curriculum is developed online. Part of the content, skills and strategies that were previously delivered in the classroom are now designed and studied in a virtual environment.

Blended Learning Features

Blended learning is constructed under specific features which are the primary foundation for this concept. These features include:

Withdrawal and Disconnectness

In this respect, Kintu, Zhu and Kagambe (2017) who feel that lack of interaction leads to withdrawal and disconnection from the teacher and the class. The problems of withdrawal, lack of concentration, and student disconnectedness are detrimental to effective learning; as alienated students are not engaged with the teacher and do not necessarily grasp what is being taught. Notably, the main issue that brought about the development of blended or hybrid learning was the challenges experienced with the new technology of face-to-face learning as a unit (Moore & Kearsely, 2011). For technology-mediated learning, Moore and Kearsely (2011) found that the major challenge to e-learning or online supported learning was that students were being left out during the learning process. This may be caused by the fact that the students are fascinated by the technological devices, especially if it is their first experience, rather than paying attention to the class proceedings.

Another reason established by Banditvilai (2016) is that reading academic text from a digital display is quite boring and brings the feeling of loneliness which may lead to withdrawal. Moore and Kearsely (2011) observe that the presence of technology-aided instruction facilities may sometime hinder the connection between teachers and students. These technological devices or platforms may act as a barrier to the cooperation and exchange between learners and teachers, and may encourage students to retreat from face-to-face instruction to the now-familiar video screen. Banditvilai (2016) observes that disconnectedness in classroom can deprive learners of the morale to learn, in that, it develops feelings of isolation. In fact, it diminishes the propensity of students to learn from each other and to uplift each other's motivation towards learning as a team. Kintu, Zhu and Kagambe (2017) therefore put a lot of emphasis on the role of interaction as a building block for blended learning. Blended learning diversifies the mode of interactions as stakeholders can interact, either face-to-face, or through online platforms. The interaction between learners, teachers, and their peers, according to Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe (2017) makes blended learning effective and avoids the challenges of withdrawal and lack of concentration. Teachers are advised on the importance of enhancing connectedness among the three elements of blended learning, teacher, learners, and mode of delivery in order to make learning effective. According to Shraim (2012), the teacher should retain the authority for controlling the amount of time used for interacting with the technological platforms, the place of learning, and the pace of instruction, including aspects such as clarification. This implies that learners should not have absolute control over the technological platforms as this would defeat the purpose of blended learning. Without a locus of control, Shraim (2012) feels that the aspect of interaction can be misused, leading to the failure of blended learning. Banditvilai (2016) also finds it paramount for educators to ask logical questions regarding the issue of "connectedness" in the implementation of blended learning. Such questions can include:

- 1) How often teacher-students meet face-to-face as compared to online experiences?
- 2) What should be accomplished in either one of the learning platforms?
- 3) How do these platforms enhance social interactions, among other considerations?

These questions as posed by Banditvilai (2016) have the effect of enhancing the element of control, to ensure that the interactions are not overemphasized at the expense of learning outcomes.

System Quality

System quality is another design feature discussed by Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe (2017) as a building block for blended learning. In this case, the authors suggest that the mode of content delivery or the technological mediated platform for instruction issuance should meet a certain threshold for educators to get maximum performance out of them. As observed, technology is a key factor of blended learning systems; it is vital to ensure that the technology used is of high quality, reliable, and it is easy to navigate. Moore and Kearsely (2011) castigate the use of obsolete technology in education, saying that it is bound to yield poor results that will undermine the learning initiatives and may fail to meet the learning objectives. Confirming this, Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe (2017) show that poor technology quality gives less satisfaction to the users, affecting their attitudes and motivation towards blended learning. According to Osgerby (2013), the current rapid technological advances, users are fully engaged with

platforms that are fast, efficient, and reliable. Hence, efficient technology yields greater user satisfaction. Technological quality thus plays a key role in satisfaction, as Shraim (2012) confirms. Therefore, the importance of examining technology quality in order to get the best out of blended learning programs should be the focus.

Learner Satisfaction

In the same vein, Banditvilai (2016) finds that learner satisfaction is paramount for positive learning outcomes such as performance, motivation, satisfaction, and knowledge construction moving on, face-to-face support is a core feature for blended learning as scholars have noted the importance of interaction in learning. Osgerby (2013) is wary of teachers who tend to lean on one method in hybrid learning programmes, purporting that this imbalance does not produce the expected learning outcomes. It is therefore important to enhance technology with face-to-face experience in the classroom set up. Osgerby (2013) further maintains that the face-to-face experience gives the teacher the best opportunity to understand the learners' abilities and inadequacies. From this, the teacher can identify what needs to be done to improve knowledge construction among learners. Face-to-face support also yields more social interaction and sharpens communication skills that are developed within the classroom environment.

Finally, Osgerby (2013) notes that learners are more successful if they are in a position to interact with their teachers and peers so that they can make clarifications, exchange ideas, and learn from one another. Face-to-face sessions can be enhanced through other elements such as humor, seeking differing opinions, non-verbal expressions, gestures, and even giving practical examples in class (Osgerby, 2013). The bottom line is that teachers should not hide behind the "technology veil" and resume the traditional role of the lecturer, or on the other hand, rely too heavily on one-way technology. Blended learning calls for the use of both types of delivery interchangeably and exhaustively, to make the best out of all elements and achieve the outlined objectives (Shraim, 2012).

Advantages of Blended Learning in Language Teaching

Different scholars have outlined varied ways in which BL enhances language teaching based on the findings from their studies. According to Shraim (2012), language teaching is a challenging process, and facilitators prefer a teaching method that usually has the best learning outcomes. In the same context, Wang, Shan, Novak and Xioayan (2009) assert that one of the main advantages created by BL is support for different methods of language instruction. The purpose of their study was to ensure that teachers had a clear understanding of what benefits each method contributes in BL (Wang et al., 2009). Each teaching approach has different challenges, and Wang et al. (2009) found that blending the online and classroom instruction helps to address the inefficiencies identified in each approach. Wang et al. (2009) believe it is essential to blend the two methods for the purpose of creating a more effective learning process. Aborisade (2013) believes that the online platform expands learning materials and improves accessibility for learners as a support to traditional classroom instruction. This is an advantage in language teaching as the students are exposed to varied learning aids (recorded drills and conversation practice) which all contribute to broadening their knowledge. In face-to-face interaction, learners depend on the material given by the teacher, which may not be sufficient for their language learning. This deficiency is addressed through BL, as students have increased access to their practice with the material.

Similarly, face-to-face interaction supports technology's role in BL by infusing other aspects of learning such as daily conversation, social networking, and group collaboration that would not be addressed if the teacher used only digital learning approaches (Akintunde, 2023a). Often, online learning only covers a few learning skills, and may not acquaint students with all the language skills needed in daily life. Siew-Enga and Muuk, (2015) notes that classroom interaction is essential to effective public speaking. Embracing online learning exclusively can prevent the students from developing such special skills as public speaking. Face-to-face interactions enhance online learning in this area by creating an environment that supports interaction and enhances speaking skills in the target language (Akintunde, 2023b).

According to Aborisade (2013), the main aim for language learning is to be equipping learners with the target language skills that will help the learner to address real-life situations. Public speaking is one of the fundamental ways of expressing oneself and it is best cultivated in the face-to-face interaction in the classroom. However, it should be noted that regular practice is fundamental in all language learning and it is vital for students to interact in the target language. It is also worth-noting that collaboration in the classroom setting is associated with group support for problem-solving skills (Wang et al., 2009). This means that learners will be able to handle a task as a team and thus learn how to maximize their cognitive abilities in problem solving. Moreover, technology-mediated platforms also enhance face-to-face language teaching in development of writing skills. Technology gives learners a platform to practice their writing abilities and receive expert guidance. As opposed to other methods such as task-based learning that concentrate on oral practice alone, BL enhances writing skills, reading, and speaking, which are all fundamental to increasing English comprehension and communication (Akintunde, 2023b).

It is evident that the key advantage of blended learning is that both face-to-face and technology teaching methods support each other, and address the inadequacies found in either approach alone, so as to achieve the best results in language teaching. Finally, Shea (2017) asserts that BL has six paramount outcomes in language teaching: pedagogical richness, access to knowledge, social interaction, personal agency, cost-effectiveness, and ease of revision. As mentioned by Wang et al. (2009), BL is effective in increasing inputs and outcomes. This means that learners have diverse sources for their materials, leading to an increased pool of knowledge.

In sum, online and other technological teaching materials enhance ease of revision due to the accessibility of learning materials. It may also be associated with greater access to learning where the facilitator can manage various learners at the time. The goal of social interaction has also been addressed, as it responds to the challenges of disorientation and disconnection in the classroom. Akintunde (2023a) confirms that reading academic text from a digital display may be problematic, and students' achievements from online reading tend to be lower. Online learning alone creates a possibility of loneliness or social detachment, which are major detractors to language learning. But BL, according to Aborisade (2013), succeeds by providing an opportunity for combining online and F2F learning experiences which bridge the gap of social detachment. However, Shea (2017) acknowledges something of great interest to language teachers: pedagogical richness.

Pedagogical Richness

Pedagogy is broadly defined as the art and practice of direct instructional teaching. Shea (2017) calls pedagogical richness as the transition from a presentation format to

an active learning format. Comas-Quinn (2011) defines the concept of pedagogy as a special ability that enables the teacher to integrate, transform, and represent content and knowledge, using approaches that are easy for the learner to comprehend. Pedagogical richness, according to these authors, combines subject matter and content knowledge for greater student understanding. Kintu, Zhu, and Kagambe (2017) further posits that pedagogical richness is instrumental in the teacher's understanding of how particular topics, problems or issues are organized, presented, and adapted to address myriad students' abilities and interests. In language teaching, it is important to pinpoint the learner's specific needs to achieve language proficiency. As reported by Shraim (2012), each student can have a special ability or deficiency when it comes to language learning. It is up to the teacher to pinpoint these abilities and inadequacies and establish the most appropriate ways to respond to them. BL comes in as a facilitator of pedagogical richness in an array of situations.

First, F2F class experience enhances social interactions where the teacher is able to pinpoint the specific abilities of the student (Siew-Enga & Muuk, 2015). Thus, F2F instructions allow students to express ideas, interact with others, build speaking skills, and improve cultural understanding of the target language. Second, technology gives the teacher a spotlight on each student's individual capabilities, or what Shea (2017) calls personal agency.

With reference to Aborisade (2013), technological platforms engage learners in an individual presentation and it is easy for the teacher to learn about their cognitive skills, thinking patterns, and knowledge constructivism. Comas-Quinn (2011) feel that the main impetus of pedagogical richness is that it brings a rendezvous between knowledge representation of subject matter by the teacher, learning difficulties and conceptions among the students. It therefore gives the facilitator an advantage to address these issues for the purpose of enhancing language skills. Aborisade (2013) asserts that blended learning and pedagogical richness integrate three important teaching dimensions: knowledge constructivism, social constructivism, and problem-based learning.

Knowledge Construction

The concept of knowledge construction is construed in the basis that effective learning is achieved when there is active learning (Siew-Enga & Muuk, 2015). Shea (2017) mentioned earlier that pedagogical richness transforms learning from mere presentation to active learning. BL helps learners to initiate, discover, and accomplish the procedurals of knowledge construction in the classroom set-up (Shea, 2017). This implies that learners can stimulate their cognitive abilities to create knowledge that has positive outcome in relation to what they are learning. Siew-Enga and Muuk (2015) assert that online discussion prompts learners into the steps given to construct meaning out of the target language through the process of giving and receiving knowledge amongst themselves. Siew-Enga and Muuk (2015) affirm that the ability to produce knowledge and distribute it is initiated by knowledge constructivism.

Social Interaction

Social constructivism theory is concerned with how learners interact with each other. It is based on the belief that most people learn as a result of social interaction and collaboration with others. Shraim (2012) argue that the new technology platforms provide an array of socialization spaces where learners can exchange ideas and collaborate in completing a task. This suggests that it is a critical benefit of BL for language teaching.

Problem-Based Learning

Pedagogical richness involves problem-based learning which requires the use of real-world scenarios, social learning and application of knowledge to new situations. In language teaching, Grgurovic (2011) believes it is paramount to embrace practice using the authentic materials of the target language. This ensures that learners are in a position to get the exact meaning of words, sentences, and structures in the target language. Basically, there are some aspects such as sociolinguistics that cannot be taught in a classroom set-up unless the learner immerses into the community or professionals using the language to absorb such meanings. BL has managed to solve this issue by providing an opportunity where the learner can interact directly with practical scenarios using the target language, probably through online platforms such as video-conferencing. Problem-based learning is multi-faceted as it imposes both language skills and at the same time enables learners to solve real-life scenarios (Poon, 2013). The core purpose of learning a language as observed is to interact and address issues that are facing societies. Traditional learning only provides the basics through a presentation format, but lacks the window for interactive learning.

Disadvantages of a Blended Learning Course

There are followers and opponents of BL courses. Nowadays, many Foreign Language (FL) teachers still appear to be reluctant to integrate technology in the FL course for some reasons. First of all, using modern technologies in some cases may appear to be too novel and complicated for an average user. Secondly, it is commonly believed that some students may have problems with planning, and fighting procrastination. It means that for some of them it is difficult to find 'appropriate' time for learning if they have too much flexibility. Another drawback is that instruction in the e-learning component of the course is dependent on technology use. However, there are solutions to the problems. For example, those teachers who are 'digital immigrants' can enrol in various teacher development courses that would introduce them to the main aspects of using new technologies in the FL classroom (Grgurovic, 2011)). As regards fighting procrastination, it is imperative to provide students with effective ways of time management and, at least, basic knowledge of soft skills which are useful in everyday life.

Implication for Pedagogy

One of the most fundamental conclusions that can be drawn from this paper is the aspect of pedagogy richness as a result of blended learning. As noted by Comas-Quinn (2011), pedagogy is the teacher's ability to understand various teaching methods that can be embraced in order to get the maximum learning outcomes in language teaching. Pedagogical richness assumes that the teacher is well conversant with the area of concern, which is the subject matter, and has the ability to transfer that knowledge to the student. Therefore, pedagogical richness is an integral tool for transforming language skills from the teacher to the learners. Miyazoe and Anderson (2010, p. 186) explain that teaching and learning are "two sides of a coin that need to be flipped simultaneously" in order to acquire language skills effectively. The teacher needs to be part of both sides of the coin: to demonstrate exemplary skills in teaching and also in helping learners to absorb what is being taught. In most cases, teachers may be professionals in their fields but lack the ability to make learners construct that knowledge in their mind set. BL therefore solves this inability by instilling pedagogical richness in language teachers.

A new language cannot be learned or acquired through presentation only; learners must decipher the teacher's instructions and construct their own usages (Miyazoe & Anderson, 2010). The same rule applies in language teaching where students have to contextualize the instructions given in order to benefit from the material. BL gives myriad opportunities for teachers to connect both orally and through technology-mediated platforms. As observed above, BL embraces technological integration, which means that the facilitators have to infuse digital technologies into their teaching pedagogies. In language learning, technology is constantly used for information search and social interaction which means that it has to be part of the lesson design. Starkey (2010) insists that teachers using BL should have the ability to develop the potential of digital technology and understand that there is a gap between applications and knowledge creation in the digital age. BL comes to the rescue of teachers by giving the ability to create knowledge whilst using technological mediated platforms in language learning. In fact, Starkey (2010) asserts that ICT tools have blossomed and at times teachers can be overwhelmed in keeping up with the developments. As a result, pedagogical models drawn from BL are integral in enhancing technological mediated teaching.

Conclusion

BL in language teaching is that it delivers a number of advantages for language teaching. First, there are traditional didactic or the expository approaches where content consists of textbook, lectures, and guided or facilitated discussion. This expository approach is then fused with active learning, where a student engages in varied exercises that are at a controlled pace and time. Also, BL collaborates and integrates with interactive learning, since content is co-created among students who are interacting with the teacher. In BL, technology is used to support all the three concepts; traditional didactic, active learning, and interactive learning. As a result, the teacher is exposed to varied approaches that address unique and specific needs of the language learner. Most importantly, BL can bring a larger pool of learning resources and materials, tools that are useful in knowledge expansion. Traditional methods are limited to the brick-and-mortar material pool, which limits students to the teacher's instructions, school library and textbook. BL aids in increasing the knowledge pool and even in reducing the time consumed in language teaching class work. At the same time, it is important to note that BL has some fundamental differences that should be addressed before embracing its use in language learning.

Recommendations

It is necessary to gear teacher training in the direction of facilitating positive instructor-learner relationships and building a helpful blended classroom atmosphere. To fulfill this goal, on the one hand, teachers need new skills that are obviously different from those in traditional instruction. On the other hand, researchers and practitioners also need to work more on how technology could be blended with traditional methods in order to facilitate and foster more successful communication.

Teachers' role is that of a provider of learning content or as an authority to offer correct answers. Teachers are still greatly needed by students for their timely and adequate guidance, direction, feedback and comments while students are learning in blended learning environment. Thus, how to provide effective guidance and feedback

might be the focus of teacher training and blended learning in the future. Indeed, greater efforts are needed to supervise, monitor and track students' learning in different ways. This is probably much more crucial than in face-to-face learning contexts.

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